

SoilX

Illustrated guide to identify tillage, sowing and mechanical weeding operations

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1 Introduction

This illustrated guide is intended to facilitate the identification of tillage and mechanical weeding implements to collect the management information of long term experiments (LTE) for the SoilX project. SoilX is an EJP SOIL funded research project.

The presented images for illustrating purposes, real machines may differ from the images.

The machines are listed according to the concept of primary tillage, seedbed preparation, sowing and stubble cultivation that is further elaborated in KTBL (2020). In brief, KTBL (2020) distinguishes between:

- Stubble cultivation (Fig. 2) is only a shallow cultivation method to loosen, mix or invert the soil after harvesting to promote the emergence of volunteer grain and weed seeds, with a cultivation depth of up to 15 cm.
- Primary tillage is a loosening, mixing or inverting form of cultivation with a cultivation depth between 15 cm and 35 cm. Primary tillage takes place prior to seedbed preparation and sowing
- Seedbed preparation or secondary tillage is limited to an operation depth of 5-10 cm. The seed horizon is crumbled finely, loosened and reconsolidated to ensure optimal seed germination.
- Sowing is the defined placement of seed at an optimal depth for the type of crop. It is carried out as row sowing, band sowing or broadcast sowing.

All description are derived from the sources mentioned in the reference section and only slightly modified for better understanding. Images are either derived from the sources in the reference section or from the companies mentioned underneath the images. Lemken GmbH, Tehnos d.o.o and Einböck GmbH are generously allowing the use of their images.

2 Tillage Operations

2.1 Primary tillage

Plough	
<p>Loosening and mixing, inversion primary tillage. Intensive soil cultivation, very little covering with plant residues on the surface. Minimum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered stubble cultivation).</p> <p>Can be operated in-furrow (left) or on-land (right).</p>	
Aliases: Moldboard plough	Sources: KTBL (2020), Lemken GmbH (Germany)
Plough with packer	
<p>Loosening and mixing, inversion primary tillage with consolidation and breaking of clods. Intensive soil cultivation, leaving very little covering with plant residues on the surface. Crumbling and consolidation through trailing packer. Minimum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered stubble cultivation).</p> <p>Can be operated in-furrow or on-land (see above).</p>	
Aliases: Moldboard plough with packer	Sources: KTBL (2020)
Spading machine	
<p>Loosening and mixing, non-inversion primary tillage. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 85 %.</p>	
Aliases:	Sources: KTBL (2020)

Deep tiller

Loosening and mixing, non-inversion primary tillage with driven tools. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 85 %. Minimum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered seedbed preparation).

Aliases: deep rototiller

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Heavy-duty cultivator (for primary tillage)

Loosening and mixing, non-inversion primary tillage. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 50-75 %. Minimum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered seedbed preparation). Minimum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered stubble cultivation).

Different chisel forms exist: (A) reversible pike point, (B) reversible straight point, (C) reversible twistet point, (D) reversible shovel point, (E) shovel, (F) sweeps.

Aliases: Chisel plough

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Disk-harrow

Loosening and mixing, non-inversion primary tillage. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 40-60 %. Minimum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered seedbed preparation).

Aliases: Disk Plough

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Strip tiller (for primary tillage)

Partial strip-wise loosening, non-inversion primary tillage - strip-wise cultivation of the seed rows before sowing. Less than 50 % of the total area is cultivated. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 60-70 %. Minimum operation depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered seedbed preparation).

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Subsoiler

The subsoiler is a loosening, non-inversion primary tillage tool, that is similar to a chisel plow. It is typically designed to penetrate 30 to 55 cm deep to alleviate soil compaction. Different shanks exist: Straight, parabolic, bent leg (from left to right)

Aliases:

Sources: NRCS (2010)

Paraplough

The purpose of the Paraplough is to loosen compacted soil layers 30 to 40 cm deep and still maintain high surface residue levels. The Paraplough lifts and loosens the soil.

Aliases: Para-till

Sources: NRCS (2017), NRCS (2010)

Other primary tillage operations (without images):

- Separator: Operation to separate stones, typically used for potatoes

2.2 Seedbed preparation

Seedbed combination	
<p>The seed horizon is loosened and crumbled with towed, not driven implements and reconsolidated with a roller. The implement speed is equivalent to the driving speed.</p>	
Aliases:	Sources: KTBL (2020)
Strip tiller (for seedbed preparation)	
<p>The seed horizon is partially strip-wise loosened and crumbled with towed, not driven implements and reconsolidated with a roller. The implement speed is equivalent to the driving speed. The implement reduces covering of the cultivated surface with organic residues by 50-60 %. Maximum depth is approx. 10 cm (otherwise it is considered primary tillage).</p>	
Aliases:	Sources: KTBL (2020)
Rotary harrow	
<p>The seed horizon is loosened and crumbled with driven implements operating around a vertical axis, and reconsolidated with a roller. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 30 %. The implement speed is equivalent to the driving speed in interaction with the circumferential speed of 3-6 m/s. Tines are straight, trailed or “on grip”.</p>	
Aliases: Rotary cultivator (tines “on grip”)	Sources: KTBL (2020)

Tine rotor

The seed horizon is loosened and crumbled with driven implements operating around the transverse axis and reconsolidated with a roller (or not). The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 50-75 %. The implement speed is equivalent to the driving speed in interaction with the circumferential speed of 4-8 m/s.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Tiller

The seed horizon is loosened and crumbled with driven implements operating around the transverse axis, and reconsolidated with a roller (or not). The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 50-75 %. The implement speed is equivalent to the driving speed in interaction with the circumferential speed of 4-8 m/s. Maximum depth is approx. 10 cm (otherwise it is considered primary tillage).

Aliases: Rotovator, rototiller

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Other seedbed preparation operations (without images):

- Bedder: Operation to form dams or beds, e.g. for potatoes or carrots

2.3 Stubble cultivation

Mulching

Mulching involves shredding of above-ground organic material like stubbles, grasses or cover crops and covering the soil with the shredded material without any intervention in the soil.

Aliases:

Sources: Tehnos, d.o.o. (Slovenia)

Tine weeder (for stubble cultivation)

Mixing, very shallow stubble cultivation. Even spreading of the straw covering and unroots weeds. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 5 %.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020), Mohler et al. (2021)

Rotary weeder (for stubble cultivation)

Mixing, very shallow stubble cultivation with a rotating device. Even spreading of the straw covering and unrooting weeds.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Ring cutter

Loosening and mixing, non-inversion stubble cultivation. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 10 %

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Roller (for stubble cultivation)

Rollers firm the seed bed or consolidate loose soil. This contributes to better seed soil contact and is important for establishment of small seeded crops like forages.

Aliases:

Sources: NRCS (2017)

Knife roller

Crushing, cutting and mixing effect on organic residues and cover crops. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 10 %.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Short-disk harrow

Mixing, non-inversion stubble cultivation. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 40-60 %. Maximum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered primary tillage).

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Spade roller harrow

Mixing, non-inversion stubble cultivation. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 40-60 %.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Fine cultivator

Loosening and mixing, non-inversion stubble cultivation (shallow). The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 20-40 %.

Different chisel forms exist: (A) reversible pike point, (B) reversible straight point, (C) reversible twisted point, (D) reversible shovel point, (E) shovel, (F) sweeps.

Aliases: Chisel

Sources: KTBL (2020), NRCS (2010)

Heavy-duty cultivator (for stubble cultivation)

Loosening and mixing, non-inversion stubble cultivation (deep). The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 50-75 %. Maximum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered primary tillage).

Different chisel forms exist: (A) reversible pike point, (B) reversible straight point, (C) reversible twisted point, (D) reversible shovel point, (E) shovel, (F) sweeps.

Aliases: Chisel plough

Sources: KTBL (2020), NRCS (2010)

Skim plough

Inversion stubble cultivation. Little covering with plant residues on the surface (on < 10 % of ground covering). Maximum depth is approx. 15 cm (otherwise it is considered primary tillage).

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Other stubble cultivation operations (without images):

- Straw harrow: Harrow, used to distribute residues evenly and level field surface (e.g., in no-till systems)

3 Sowing Operations

Seed drill (classic)

Seed placement in rows or bands at the defined placement depth. Seed feed through dosing units and mechanical or pneumatic conveyance and distribution.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Single-grain seed drill (classic)

Seed placement in rows with defined longitudinal grain spacing at the defined placement depth. Seed feed through dosing units and mechanical or pneumatic conveyance and distribution.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Direct seed drill (*no till*)

Seed placement in rows or bands with no prior tillage. Seed feed through dosing units and mechanical or pneumatic conveyance and distribution. Soil disturbance is not more than needed for seed and fertiliser placement. Sowing is carried out on less than 1/3 of the row width Cultivation depth is the seed placement depth.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Single-grain direct seed drill (no till)

Seed placement is carried out without previous tillage. Seed placement in rows with defined longitudinal grain spacing at the defined placement depth. Seed feed through dosing units and mechanical or pneumatic conveyance and distribution. Sowing is carried out on less than 1/3 of the row width Cultivation depth is the seed placement depth.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Broadcast seeder

Broadcast seeding is a method of seeding that involves scattering seed, by hand or mechanically, over a relatively large area.

Aliases:

Sources: Custom, pictures from IRRI and Gmihail (Serbian Wikipedia)

Grassland reseeder

Seed placement is carried out without previous tillage. Seed placement in rows at the defined placement depth. Seed feed through dosing units and mechanical or pneumatic conveyance and distribution.

Aliases:

Sources: KTBL (2020)

Roller (for sowing)

Rollers firm the seed bed or consolidate loose soil. This contributes to better seed soil contact and is important for establishment of small seeded crops like forages.

Aliases:

Sources: NRCS (2017)

Other sowing operations (without images):

- Potato planter: Planting potatoes into ridges

4 Mechanical weeding operations

Tine weeder (for weeding)	
<p>Mixing, very shallow stubble cultivation. Even spreading of the straw covering and unroots weeds. The implement reduces covering of the surface with organic residues by 5 %.</p>	
Aliases: Tine harrow	Sources: KTBL (2020), Mohler et al. (2021)

Rotary weeder (for weeding)	
<p>Mixing, very shallow stubble cultivation with a rotating device. Even spreading of the straw covering and unrooting weeds.</p>	
Aliases: Rotary harrow	Sources: KTBL (2020), Einböck GmbH (Austria)

Tine hoe	
<p>Inter-rows soil cultivation with shovels, sweeps or pike implements.</p>	
Aliases: cultivator	Sources: Einböck GmbH (Austria), Mohler et al. (2021)

Rotary hoe

Ground-driven implement that uses a series of wheels with metal spoons radiating out.

Aliases:

Sources: Einböck GmbH (Austria), Mohler et al. (2021)

Finger hoe

Designed to mount on a row-crop cultivator to provide in-row and near-row weeding that cannot be achieved by sweeps and shovels alone.

Aliases:

Sources: Einböck GmbH (Austria), Mohler et al. (2021)

Star hoe

Usually consists of gangs of "spider" ground driven wheels with two gangs working in each inter-row. Depending on the setting of the gangs, soil flow is strictly toward or away from the row.

Aliases:

Sources: Mohler et al. (2021)

5 References

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